

PEER-REVIEWED ARTICLE

Learning from the Palestinian people: Eight lessons for psychology[#]

David Pavón-Cuéllar* Universidad Michoacana de San Nicolás de Hidalgo, Morelia, Mexico

ABSTRACT

A political–epistemological shift is proposed whereby psychology, abandoning its position of presumed omniscience, humbly unlearns what it knows and replaces it with everything it can learn from the Palestinian people and their spokespersons, including psychologists, psychiatrists, and psychotherapists. The proposal is for psychology to be reinvented and taught by the Palestinian people rather than continually applied to them by seeking to explain their resistance to the Israeli occupation and to understand and address the psychological effects of such an occupation. This article begins by reflecting on psychology’s relationship with the Palestinian people. Subsequently, after questioning the conventional and dominant approaches to the misnamed ‘Israeli–Palestinian conflict’, the article discusses alternative critical proposals and illustrates how they relate to the Palestinian people and their struggle for liberation. These proposals allow us to give voice to the people and to enunciate eight lessons they offer psychology and the mental health field: collectivisation, connection with the people, a view from below, decolonisation, territorialisation, remembrance, resubjection, and repoliticisation.

KEYWORDS: Palestine; Israel; occupation; psychology; politics

INTRODUCTION

In a fascinating article, Pedro Costa and Kíssila Mendes (2025) recapitulate and systematise what can be learned from Palestinian psychology, particularly the critical communitarian paradigm developed at Birzeit University in the West Bank. Costa and Mendes’ work is

*Contact details: davidpavoncuellar@gmail.com

[#]This article was previously published in Spanish as ‘Ocho lecciones del pueblo palestino para la psicología’ in *Teoría y Crítica de la Psicología*, 22(2025), and is reproduced with permission.

<https://www.teocripsi.com/ojs/index.php/TCP/article/view/499>

valuable not only for its synthetic and reflective nature but also for its explication of a crucial point of the paradigm they present. This point correlates the transcendence of psychological knowledge and its consubstantiality with the people among whom it was born.

Costa and Mendes understand that it is the Palestinian people who teach us with their critical communitarian psychology. We can learn so much from this psychological proposal because it gives voice to a popular constellation of knowledge and struggles. The purpose must then be, in the terms of Costa and Mendes (2025), not to 'teach lessons to a people who resist and are the moral compass of our times in matters of struggle' but to learn from them and to 'share their voice, their knowledge and their struggles' (p. 3). In other words, we should listen to 'the voices of the Palestinians themselves' and 'equip ourselves with these voices' by becoming 'a space for their vocalisation' (p. 12). When we proceed in this way, we are proceeding similarly to Birzeit's critical community psychologists, who radically subvert and transform psychology by enriching it with everything they learn from Palestinians.

One of the most important lessons of Birzeit's critical community psychology is to be formed in the school of the people: to assimilate to the people, to *become them*, to be part of them, and to struggle with them. Based on the political–epistemological shift implied by this lesson, this article attempts to reconstruct part of what the Palestinian people can teach psychology through mediations such as their psychological proposals. The emphasis is no longer, as in Costa and Mendes (2025), what Palestinian psychology can teach us, but what the Palestinian people can teach psychology through their psychological proposals. However, as was just noted, the very idea that psychology should receive lessons from the people, not vice versa, is a lesson from Palestinian psychology. Correspondingly, this article can be read as a simple continuation of Costa and Mendes' work.

Our starting point is the psychological approaches to the misnamed 'Israeli–Palestinian conflict'. After identifying and questioning guiding axes of the conventional and dominant approaches to the 'conflict', we focus on alternative critical proposals and demonstrate how they relate to the Palestinian people and their struggle for liberation. This, then, allows us to give voice to the people, themselves, and state eight lessons that psychologists can learn from them.

We listen to the people after the psychologists. We then shift from psychological accounts of the 'conflict' to the Palestinian people's possible contributions to the psychology field. Once psychology is dismissed as a source of learning, our interest in learning lies in the Palestinian people and their defensive resistance, not in their 'conflict' with Israel, much less in Israeli expansionist Zionism: a Zionism from which we cannot learn, except what it reveals as a 'symptom', as Agustín Palmieri (2023) rightly observed.

What manifests symptomatically through Zionism is what the Palestinian people fight in resisting the Israeli yoke: capitalism, imperialism, colonialism, racism, etc. (Abdo, 2024; Ayyash, 2024; Losurdo, 2020). All this constitutes the historical reality in which what the

Palestinian people can teach psychology has developed. These teachings are inseparable from the reality in which they originate, which must be acknowledged as its victims know it (Said, 1979). This requires tearing apart political and media images designed to distort and obscure reality.

One of the images that deforms historical reality is precisely that of a 'conflict' between Israel and Palestine. There is no 'conflict' here, but a unilateral Israeli offensive against the Palestinian people to annihilate them and seize their lands, as well as the desperate defensive efforts of these people in a colonial situation characterised by imbalanced forces. What we are dealing with, in other words, is resistance and a struggle to survive amid ethnic cleansing, resulting in territorial dispossession (Pappé, 2007). In these conditions, the image of a conflict between Israelis and Palestinians is as misleading as that of a conflict between European settlers and Native Americans, between Nazis and Jews, or between whites and black South Africans during Apartheid.

Tearing apart images similar to the 'Israeli–Palestinian conflict' is necessary to begin to understand the underlying reality. It is also an indispensable prerequisite for understanding both the lessons we learn from Palestinians and what distinguishes them from the psychological work we discuss below. Incidentally, by the way, such work normally clings to the misleading image of the 'conflict' in which it situates its objects of study.

THE PSYCHOLOGY OF THE 'CONFLICT' AND ITS EFFECTS

The so-called 'conflict' has fuelled countless research works in psychology. Some of these address the 'conflict' psychologically as such, attempting to explain and resolve it. Others direct their psychological attention towards the effects of the 'conflict' on subjectivity, seeking to understand and treat them. Therefore, we can speak, respectively, of a psychology of the 'conflict' and a psychology of its effects. The former is predominantly social, political, and cultural. The latter is more clinical, psychiatric, psychotherapeutic, and community based.

The psychology of the 'conflict' focuses on psychological factors that explain the conflict and operate equally in Israelis and Palestinians. Among these factors are a lack of mutual recognition (Kelman, 1987), social beliefs (Rouhana and Bar-Tal, 1998), an absence of listening and dialogue (Chaitin, 2011), and a combination of psychological resistance, mutual delegitimation, past experiences, historical perceptions, entrenched ideologies, and religious beliefs (Ben-Meir, 2023). So much weight is given to these factors that it would seem that addressing them would be sufficient to resolve the conflict.

Conflict psychology often assumes that the key to resolving the conflict is for Palestinians and Israelis to no longer delegitimise each other, to recognise each other, to listen to each other, to engage in dialogue and to change their ideologies, social beliefs, and historical

perceptions. Some experts even openly claim that psychological factors are the most important factors explaining the 'conflict', since the 'conflict' is fundamentally psychological (e.g., Ben-Meir, 2023). This blatant psychologisation allows the depoliticisation of the conflict, obscuring its political core and its material historic, economic, and even military aspects.

Unlike the psychology of the 'conflict', with its irresistible propensity to psychologise, the psychology of the effects of the 'conflict' focuses on effects that are already psychological, which would apparently make research somewhat immune to psychologisation. The effects of the Israeli–Palestinian 'conflict' that have been studied are mainly trauma and post-traumatic stress disorder, on which there are dozens of studies and systematic and meta-analytic reviews of existing research (Agbaria et al., 2021; Marie et al., 2020). Other possible effects studied have been cognitive, affective, and behavioural changes that do not reach the threshold for post-traumatic stress disorder (Ayer et al., 2017), violent and antisocial behaviours (Dubow et al., 2019), depression, stress, and anxiety (Aldabbour et al., 2024), and insomnia and other sleep disorders (Mahamid et al., 2025).

When examining the effects of the Israeli–Palestinian 'conflict', many psychologists and psychiatrists have also studied mitigating factors, such as parental expressions of affection among Palestinian children (Punamäki et al., 2001) or, among Gazan adolescents, optimistic attitudes, greater self-regulation, stronger coping skills, and a perception that the family represents the world as understandable (Aitcheson et al., 2017). Finally, building on works on the effects of the 'conflict' and its mitigating factors, research has attended to the best means to treat the effects of the 'conflict', ranging from changing historical and identity narratives (Hammack, 2010a, 2010b) to prolonged exposure cognitive behavioural therapy for healing post-traumatic stress disorder (Bdier & Mahamid, 2023) and techniques such as imagining a safe place and forgiveness-focused meditations (El-Astal, 2016).

In all cases, palliative care alleviates the symptoms because it cannot cure the disease. Thus, the psychology of the effects of the 'conflict' concerns pathological effects because it cannot end the cause. Palestinians must accept it, resigning themselves to the Israeli occupation with its high dose of direct and structural violence, bombings, indiscriminate murders, arbitrary impoverishments, and strategy of systematically impoverishing a population.

What the State of Israel perpetrates intervenes as an independent variable, as an implacable fatality in the psychology of the effects of the 'conflict'. This psychology can only comfort the traumatised but cannot confront the traumatic event. By being unable to provide a safe place, it can only offer the imagination of a safe place, as in El-Astal's (2016) technique. Thus, the psychology of the conflict's effects betrays its own misery, its own helplessness, if not sometimes an element of cowardice or complicity, which forces one to resign oneself and to accept the unacceptable, passing it off as acceptable.

PALESTINIAN CRITICAL PSYCHOLOGY

All the State of Israel's violence tends to appear acceptable or, at least, inevitable and unchangeable in the research and interventions that address the effects of the 'conflict'. If only for this reason, all these psychological works would be as politically problematic and open to critique as the previously discussed psychology that deals directly with the 'conflict' and psychologises it to explain and resolve it. We understand, then, why an alternative current has emerged among psychologists, psychiatrists, and psychotherapists who critically and reflexively turn against the academic and professional psychological work related to the Israeli occupation of Palestine.

The psychology of 'conflict' and of its effects has been challenged by authors who may be designated 'Palestinian critical psychologists'. Although some were not originally from territory stretching from the Jordan River to the Mediterranean, this does not prevent them from maintaining an essential connection with the Palestinian people, their experiences, and their aspirations.

Among the leading exponents of this emerging critical psychology are community psychologist Ibrahim Makkawi, psychiatrist and psychotherapist Samah Jabr, and anthropologist, community psychologist, and decolonial feminist Lena Meari. These authors and others have criticised psychological research and interventions on the 'conflict' and its effects for several reasons, including their methodological shortcomings and their inapplicability and irrelevance to the Palestinian population (Haj-Yahia, 2007), their reductionist, individualist, and positivist tendencies (Makkawi, 2009), their liberalism and Eurocentrism (Meari, 2015), their psychologism, sterility, and complicity with Israeli colonial power (Jabr, 2024b, 2024c, 2024e), their psychological extractivism and depoliticising effects (Sheehi & Sheehi, 2022), and their decontextualisation, dehistoricisation, and misleading equation of Palestinian and Israeli violence (Hakim et al., 2022). These problems must be added to the two we identified earlier: psychologisation and the resigned acceptance of Israeli violence against the Palestinian people.

The various problems of the psychologies of the 'conflict' and of its effects can be partially explained by their disconnection from the Palestinian people with their firm collective identity, history, and memory, territory and daily experience with war and misery, fears and suffering under Israeli violence, yearning for liberation, political commitment, and spirit of resistance and struggle against the invader. If all this is alien to many psychologists, psychotherapists, and psychiatrists, it is because they are not Palestinian or because they live on the other side, behind the walls outside Palestine.

There are also those who, despite living in Palestine, are compelled or forced to insert themselves as depoliticised experts, academics, or professionals into the normalcy imposed by the liberal framework of the 1993 Oslo Accords. These agreements ensure a certain normal coexistence between Palestinians and Israelis despite the persisting colonisation, oppression,

and annihilation of the former by the latter (Eid, 2024). As participants in such normalcy, mental health academics and professionals must alienate themselves as part of the Palestinian people by abstracting from the real existence and experience of their brothers and sisters and from themselves as colonised, oppressed, and annihilated.

By disconnecting from Palestinians, one inevitably arrives at what Palestinian critical psychology contests. Indeed, one arrives at hypotheses, theories, conceptualisations, conclusions, proposals, and practical implementations that are inapplicable, irrelevant, reductionist, dehistoricised, and decontextualised in their Eurocentrism, liberalism, apoliticism, individualism, and psychologism. Conversely, if all this can be easily detected by exponents of Palestinian critical psychology, it is because of their connection to the Palestinian people.

By being connected to Palestinians, Makkawi, Jabr, Meari, and others can critically discern precisely where psychology fails by failing to serve Palestinians. Besides this critical capacity, critical psychologists, themselves, possess knowledge that they can pass to us after having learned it positively from Palestinians. Part of this learning is evident in the eight lessons summarised below.

CONNECTION WITH THE PEOPLE: AGAINST ACADEMIC AND PROFESSIONAL ISOLATION

The first lesson of the Palestinian people is precisely to maintain a connection with them, avoiding the academic and professional isolation of psychologists who lock themselves in their institutions or organisations and obey only their logic of funding, publications, programs, projects, promotions, priorities, etc. (Makkawi, 2009, 2017). These logics constitute more obstacles than opportunities for studying people with their own logic. Properly studying people requires connecting with them according to their own logic, not our institutional logic, and on their terms, not psychology's or psychiatry's.

Instead of insisting on perceiving post-traumatic stress disorder in those who survived an Israeli bombardment, we learn from the Palestinian people everything contained in expressions such as *badany masmum*, *maqhur*, *Mazlum*, or *maksur khatry*. Translated by Jabr (2024c), those terms mean feeling their bodies are 'intoxicated, oppressed, exposed to injustice', with their 'desire shattered' (p. 57). This—not post-traumatic stress—is what Gaza's subjects have been suffering.

Individuals' experiences can only be known and understood through connection with them, with their struggles and movements, which have coordinates and terminologies differing from those of psychology and our institutions. Hence, it is essential for psychologists, as Costa and Mendes (2025) have emphasised, to go 'beyond institutionalisation' and

‘overcome the limits of psychology’, guided by struggles and movements in ‘criticising academia and psychology’ (p. 10). This critique is precisely what we find in authors who have followed the Palestinian people when critically turning against their colleagues’ psychiatric and psychological work.

A VIEW FROM BELOW: AGAINST ELITISM

Makkawi, Jabr, and others criticise psychiatrists and psychologists for not serving the Palestinian people, for not responding to their needs and aspirations, and for not relating to their history, culture, or material reality. It is as if mental health experts float in the academic and professional heights of universities and other institutions, academic publications and meetings, Western funds and scholarships, international agencies and non-governmental organisations. By positioning themselves at these heights, experts fail to see what Palestinians do, what they teach us, what can only be experienced by being below and bearing the full weight of the occupation: on the one hand, what is only known by suffering it in misery, hunger, and among the rubble, and on the other hand, what is only perceived by fighting it, in resistance, seeing it actively and collectively, through the mobilisation of the community and rootedness in the territory.

The view from below is a second lesson from the Palestinian people for psychologists and psychiatrists. This lesson challenges the elitism of psychology and psychiatry, of science and intellectuality, of academics and professionals, of their epistemic and symbolic privileges, through which they forget to be people and fantasise about knowing people objectively, from a distance, from outside and above. This top-down view, when approaching the Palestinian experience, tends to objectify it, ignore their perspectives, and adopt the perspectives of Israeli–European–American academia, international organisations, and non-governmental organisations from the Global North.

By challenging the top-down view, the Palestinian people can teach us everything they taught Makkawi (2009, 2012) through their grassroots initiatives, including community daycare schools, popular education and childcare centres, support groups, and awareness-raising strategies. In all these initiatives, the Palestinian people transcend their traumatised victimhood and teach us self-management, self-organisation, and self-determination, the spirit of resistance and struggle, all from ‘below’. One of the Palestinians’ greatest lessons from below is *‘sumud’*, the steadfastness of the olive tree, but understood metaphorically not as an individual psychological attribute but as the strength of a ‘collective, relational and resistant-politicized subject’ (Meari, 2015, p. 85). We return to this point later.

DECOLONISATION: AGAINST DOMINATION AND DEPENDENCE

Sumud lies in the strength and perseverance with which the Palestinian people resist Israeli colonisation. There is another lesson here for psychology: in the struggle for decolonisation, as well as against occupation, colonial domination and the dependence of the colonised.

The Palestinian anti-colonial and decolonising position is a fundamental lesson for a psychology that often does not even recognise its colonial functioning. In Israel, Europe, and the United States, the objectivity and universality that psychology attributes to itself allows it to hide what lies beneath, including the colonial objectification of other peoples and ethnocentric and colonising universalism. Simultaneously, in the Global South, the colonised and dependent nature of psychological theories and practices is concealed in their obsessions with neutrality and scientificity, which, if they can be so obsessive, is also due to the strength of what is concealed within them.

Psychology discovers its own colonial functioning when it encounters the Palestinian people and their anti-colonial lessons. After all, as Makkawi (2017) has noted, the colonialism against which Palestinians fight, their 'economic and political dependence', is inseparable from the colonialism of psychology, 'academic dependency among Palestinian intellectuals' (p. 484). This dependent colonialism is also inseparable from the daily dependence of every Palestinian who needs the Israeli lawyer, the Israeli hospital, and the Israeli psychologist. This dependence represents a 'barrier' to trauma treatment, as it promotes 'identification with the aggressor', as Jabr (2024a, p. 33) rightly warns. Following Jabr, we can say that colonial dependence is pathogenic, so Palestinian psychologists and psychiatrists must fight it not only for cultural and political reasons, but also because of their clinical and therapeutic responsibilities, which are oriented towards curative ends.

TERRITORIALISATION: AGAINST UNIVERSALISM

It is also to heal the Palestinian that psychoanalysts must fight their universalist tendencies, trying to overcome them to avoid segregating countless experiences that do not fit the Western universe, as Sophie Mendelsohn (2023) argues. Similar to Jabr, Mendelsohn understands that Palestinians' mental health presupposes a certain decolonisation that ensures their independence and the respectful recognition of their own cultural, social, and historical specificity. This requires relocating psychology, psychiatry, and psychoanalysis within the culture and history of Palestine, its real and symbolic territory.

The need for territorialisation is another lesson from the Palestinian people. For community psychologists in Palestine, learning this lesson has implied 'the resumption and strengthening of initiatives specific to the Palestinian people, territorialised, community-based, grassroots, bottom-up initiatives', according to Costa and Mendes (2025, p. 9). What

has been understood here, which is not usually understood in the universalism that rules psychology, is that territory is the only soil in which psychological proposals that are relevant and useful for its inhabitants can germinate, sprout, grow, and flourish.

The Palestinian teaching of necessary territorialisation was well learned by Lena Meari (2015). Meari dismisses 'discourses on trauma and human rights' that 'presuppose a specific, Western-style imaginary human', presenting it as universal and transferring it to other cultures to turn socio-political actors into 'depoliticised victims to be redeemed by specialists' (p. 81). Thus, the depoliticisation of peoples such as the Palestinians is one of the political purposes of deterritorialisation, as it operates in a universalist psychology in which cultural specificity is ignored.

REMEMBRANCE: AGAINST AMNESIA

A culture entails its historical development and insertion into the history of humanity. The memory of all this is also a mental health condition that the Palestinian people know only too well. Here is another lesson from the Palestinian people for psychology: not forgetting and not falling into an amnesia at the root of a wide range of intellectual, emotional, and behavioural disorders, as well as cultural, social, and political illnesses.

Freud (1914/1996) noted that repetition was a pathological form of remembering that which we cannot remember, that which we lack a complete, adequate, or exact, conscious recollection. From this Freudian concept, we can surmise that Zionists, even though they remember the Holocaust, differ from other members of the Jewish community by not remembering it completely, adequately, accurately, and consciously and, thus, having to repeat it unconsciously and pathologically in their relationship with the Palestinians. Perhaps Zionists are trying to remember themselves as Jews through the Palestinians. Perhaps Zionists want to make Palestinians pay for the acts committed by the Nazis, as Rudolf El-Kareh (2002) and Jacqueline Rose (2005) have suggested.

The repetition of the Jewish catastrophe, the *Shoah*, in the Palestinian catastrophe, the *Nakba*, would then be the pathological form of remembering that which cannot be remembered, perhaps because of its traumatic background, which is impossible to process. Just as Nazism, antisemitism, and Islamophobia can be considered Christian pathologies, so too can Zionism be interpreted as a pathological drift of Judaism, a disorder of Jewish memory, as Nelly Marzouka and Ricardo Mazurca (2005) have suggested.

Marzouka and Mazurca (2005) have also noted that the Palestinian people, as victims of Zionist pathological amnesia, recognise the importance of historical remembrance and collective memory in 'elaborating events in a symbolic order' and in 'understanding themselves as subjects and protagonists of history' (para. 19). The same people also know

they must recall themselves by recalling their history and be present by recalling their past as the only way to perpetuate themselves as people, as evidenced by Nur Masalha (2012).

Furthermore, as a taxi driver poetically tells the writer Lina Meruane (2024), memory allows Palestinians to preserve their territory by 'clinging to what remains of Palestine to prevent it from disappearing' (p. 45). Indeed, Palestine continues to exist because its legitimate inhabitants never tire of remembering and inhabiting it. They never relinquish what belonged and continues to belong to them by right. They do not allow Israel to achieve theft and forgetting, the swindling of the present and the past, the plundering of land and memory.

We understand that Israelis fear Palestinians' memories. Was it not inevitable that what Darwish (2024) described as 'the invaders' fear of memories' (p. 24) would eventually spread in Israel? As we have observed, memory is an indispensable ingredient of political resistance, cultural self-preservation, and historical action. This is part of what the Palestinian people can teach to forgetful, presentist, and futuristic psychologists, who exhort Palestinians to let go, stop clinging to their territory, uproot themselves, forget their past, and concentrate on their daily lives and plans. These psychologists prescribe Palestinian people to limit their memory to what is most recent, to hurry to conclude their mourning, and to overcome their traumatic experience of the previous week, without linking it to the one they have experienced since 1948 that persists in the present and threatens to eternalise in the future.

COLLECTIVISATION: AGAINST LIBERAL INDIVIDUALISM

Besides the presentist perspective, which confines subjects to the present, psychology often suffers from an individualist orientation that imprisons the same subjects in their individuality. Individualism can be as pathogenic as presentism. Just as repetition is a pathological form of remembering what cannot be remembered in any other way, many pathologies are ways we suffer individually that which cannot be processed collectively. Therefore, collectivisation can be conceptualised as an indispensable ingredient for wellbeing in general and for mental health as an aspect of wellbeing.

The Palestinian people recognise the importance of collectivisation. They act accordingly, collectivising their enormous suffering, indignation, struggle, and resistance. We have another lesson here for psychology: the principle of collectivisation, with which we should try to overcome the liberal individualism that reigns in Western psychological models. This individualism has permeated and proliferated the mental health field in Jerusalem, Gaza, and the West Bank following the Oslo Accords, but has been increasingly rejected by the psychologists, psychiatrists, and psychoanalysts instructed by the Palestinian people.

Jabr (2007/2024d) dismisses the individualisation of trauma and the possibility of individual resilience, acknowledging that the only effective resilience in Palestine is 'based on

familial foundations, social support and spiritual and ideological conviction' (p. 48). Makkawi (2009) agrees with Jabr, noting that Palestinian trauma must be 'addressed at the collective level of the Palestinian people' (p. 82), not in the individual psychological sphere. Agreeing with Jabr and Makkawi, Meari (2015) posits that the traumatic experience of Palestinians can only be adequately addressed through solidarity, the collectivisation of resistance, and especially the 'collective subjectivity cultivated through sumud', which is outside the narrow sphere of 'the subjectivity of the individualised victim: the victim of human rights violations and psychological trauma' (p. 82).

This individualisation was recently rejected by Sheehi and Sheehi (2023), who depict how isolated, imprisoned, and tortured Palestinians sustained hope, health, strength, and life thanks to their collective struggle and resistance. This element penetrated the deepest and most intimate parts of their psychic life, their 'imagination' and 'daydreaming', as evidenced by a harrowing testimony: 'They'd beat us. They'd spray us with gas, because we were proud, and strong. We were deprived of food and drink. But our food was the people of Gaza. Our drink was the people of Gaza' (Sheehi & Sheehi, 2023, pp. 4–5). It is through people that individuals resist torture. However, they resist not as individuals but as part of the people, thanks to their resistance.

The individuals who resist as people, who fully realise themselves as people thanks to their resistance, manage to overcome even their deaths. This is what Darwish (2024) represents as the final victory of the Palestinian martyr, the quintessential human, the 'grain of a dying ear of corn' who 'will fill the valley with ears of corn' (p. 7). Thus, the ears of corn in Gaza and the West Bank ceaselessly reaped by Israel's scythe are the collective form of martyrs who have sacrificed themselves as individuals by identifying with the Palestinian people. Through their sacrifices, they survive.

RESUBJECTIVISATION: AGAINST OBJECTIVISM

Identification with the Palestinian people allows the tortured individuals studied by Sheehi and Sheehi (2023) to overcome their status as simple victims and objects of torture and to resist by reconstituting themselves as subjects. Here, subjectivity can only be preserved by transcending its impotent individuality, by assuming itself as a people, by reconverting into something collective and by collectivising itself. Therefore, we can say that collectivisation conditions resubjectivisation. Unlike psychological objectivism, it represents another lesson from the Palestinian people for psychology, especially objectivist psychology, which reduces the subject to the condition of an object of knowledge, treatment, research, and reflection.

To avoid resembling the torturers in their propensity to objectify the subjective, we psychologists must learn from the Palestinian people to recognise and respect subjects as collective actors and historical agents. This requires, first, allowing them to decide who they

are, such as a young Palestinian woman who characterises herself as a 'returnee' and rejects labels such as 'refugee', which implies an 'impotence to define her identity and destiny' (Shalhoub-Kevorkian, 2020, p. 141). What we learn here from the Palestinian people is not to conceptualise them in an objectivist and reductionist way as passive objects, 'as depoliticized victims, as individualized victims' (Meari, 2015, pp. 76).

Psychological individualisation, which is inseparable from victimisation and objectification, also implies depoliticisation. On the contrary, participation in collective experiences and actions allows one to repoliticise by overcoming the condition of the victim and recovering subjectivity (Pavón-Cuéllar, 2023). By becoming collectivised, subjects acquire the strength to assert themselves as subjects and resist, which does not mean, of course, that they become resilient.

Unlike psychological resilience, political resistance is a collective capacity with which people such as Palestinians preserve themselves as subjects. This capacity is learned from childhood. We can see it, for example when children throw stones at Israeli soldiers and, thus, 'take an active role in the defence of their territory', acting 'as if they were not victims' and managing to transcend their status as individual victims by merging with the people in their struggle for 'rights, dignity and territory' (Tamimi & Takruri, 2025, p. 153). The same thing happens when other children simply assume they are the 'we who know that what must be done' is to 'stay and live' in Gaza when the Israelis do everything possible to see 'Gaza empty' (Madhoun, 2025, p. 22). Leaving Gaza empty would imply becoming the object that Israeli subjects dispose of, while persisting in filling Gaza personifies the Palestinian people as subjects.

Through collective resistance, the people manage to reverse what Jabr (2024f) describes as 'the dynamic of objectification' (p. 118), seeing it operate both in war and in aiding its victims in Palestine. Facing Palestinians' objectification by both the Israeli military and psychologists, international agencies and non-governmental organisations, Nadya Shaista Ramdjan Azizuddin (2024) proposes 'restoring the respect and dignity of the subjects, recognising their autonomy and capacity to actively participate in their own recovery process' (p. 139).

This is the same point Devin Atallah (2022) makes in her community praxis, with its horizon of solidarity. This is also what Ian Parker (2023) expects from a solidarity movement that 'must go beyond sympathy for Palestinians as victims and build solidarity with them as active agents, with all their contradictions, forging their own liberation' (p. 2). In fact, coinciding with these positions, the Palestinian people are already liberating themselves and, in the process, giving us a lesson in freedom when they clarify what they expect from us: understanding rather than victimisation, alliances rather than favours, actions of support rather than expressions of pity, solidarity rather than empathy and charity, listening rather than objectifying gazes, resonance for their word rather than prescriptions of attitudes and

behaviours similar to those of many psychologists, including some reviewed above, such as Kelman, Chaitin, and Ben-Meir.

REPOLITICISATION: AGAINST PSYCHOLOGISM

What the Palestinian people expect from us psychologists is a psychology that neither ignores nor conceals nor misinterprets and neutralises the political by psychologising it, by passing it off as something psychological. This psychology overcomes the chronic psychologism of psychologists, by which they understand and explain everything psychologically, including political issues, thus depoliticising them. Avoiding this psychologisation and depoliticisation is another lesson from the Palestinian people for psychology, a lesson in attention to the political in repoliticisation and in avoiding any form of psychologism.

Avoiding psychologism also requires delimiting the psychological, strictly circumscribing it, but not ignoring it or abandoning psychology, psychotherapy, psychiatry, and other mental health professions. A Palestinian psychiatrist such as Jabr (2007/2024d) continues to offer ‘conversations and pills’ (pp. 46). However, she knows that she cannot ‘return a dead child to its parents, an imprisoned father to his children or rebuild a demolished house’ (p. 47). Therefore, she admits that the problem ‘lies in the hands of politicians’, not in the hands of health professionals who can offer only ‘palliative treatments and awareness of what is happening in Palestine’ (pp. 47).

Iman Farajallah (2024) recognises the same thing when demonstrating how the situation in Palestine, with its ‘chronic stressors’ and its ‘cumulative trauma framework’, cannot be addressed solely through the interventions of psychologists, psychiatrists and psychotherapists, demanding political changes that will break the ‘cycle of war and violence’, ensure respect for the ‘human dignity and human rights’ of Palestinians and, above all, end the Israeli occupation and its ‘structural violence’ (pp. 132–133). The problem is political, so its resolution can only be political, not psychological, which is obvious, even though psychologists such as Ben-Meir argue otherwise out of blindness or infamy.

If the problem and its resolution are essentially political, we understand that the best treatment for the psychological effects of the problem is also political. Numerous authors have already observed this. Mohamed Altawil (2009) recalls his own childhood experience of throwing stones at Israeli soldiers, concluding that his ‘anger and actions were a form of therapy’ (p. 141). Similarly, Ramdjan Azizuddin (2004) noted ‘Palestinian women’s success in maintaining their psychological integrity is related to their political and ideological commitment’, concluding that this commitment to struggle ‘explains civilians’ endurance better than personality, mental health and other individual determinants’ (p. 133).

The endurance to which Ramdjan Azizuddin refers is among the manifestations of *sumud*. It is something we could associate with Spinoza's *conatus*, with perseverance in one's own being and with the strength of being to maintain one's existence, even in the most adverse circumstances, such as those faced by the Palestinians. For the Palestinians, as Darwish (2024) would say, *sumud* is that by which they 'persevere in what seems like death in life', but knowing that 'this which seems like death is victory' (p. 23). Let us say that the Palestinians' victory is to go through death to stay alive, to persevere, thanks to a *sumud* that is part of their being.

Sumud is an existential ontological component of Palestinians. It is important to understand it not as an individual psychological capacity, but as the Palestinian people fathom it, that is in Meari's (2015) terms, 'a psycho-affective state of mind and a political-ethical way of being that becomes an integral part of public culture' and that defines a 'collective, relational and resistant-politicized subject' (p. 85). The subject of *sumud* is something that the Palestinian people try to preserve against psychology, psychologism, psychologisation, and its effects: individualisation, depoliticisation, and objectification.

CONCLUSION

Psychologisation has been increasing in Palestine since the aforementioned Oslo Accords of 1993. These accords, deceitfully claiming to have solved the objective political problem, have shifted the emphasis towards a subjective, psychological-legal superstructure in which there is no room for the collective and politicised subject of *sumud* that fights and resists the Israeli occupier. This has led to a situation, as envisioned by Costa and Mendes (2025), in which 'seeking to suppress *sumud*, the liberal tradition of human rights and mental health—expressed by the *psy* field—has begun to hegemonise ideological constructions and modes of subjectivation' (p. 8). *Homo juridicus* and *homo psychologicus*, as individualised and depoliticised as each other, have been supplanting the only fully human being, the collective and political one, the one who has taught us so much and continues to teach us, the one who still struggles and resists the Palestinian people.

Of course, people include individuals who today have human rights and mental health that must be safeguarded. However, this is not what legal and psychological mechanisms have served. First, Israeli law has legalised illegal acts through which Palestinians have been and continue to be dispossessed of their lands, properties, and resources. Likewise, psychology has not been used so much to ensure the mental health of Palestinians as to conceal and mystify their dispossession, participating in the device by which 'the case was transformed from one of rights to one of relief and humanitarian assistance' (Shejadeh, 2025, p. 191), as a well-known Palestinian lawyer denounces when recalling why his father refused to accept support from international organisations. In the end, only dispossessed and devastated

victims remain, requiring the services of mental health professionals, where previously there were subjects with territories, property, resources, and rights.

However great their losses, the Palestinian people have managed to preserve themselves. They have achieved this on their own, not with the help of lawyers, much less thanks to psychologists, psychiatrists, and psychotherapists. Regarding the mental health field, there are certainly honourable exceptions that we have highlighted here, but these professionals have fused with the Palestinian people, defending them against the uses of psychology to neutralise them by psychologising them, pulverising them into individual elements, and objectifying and depoliticising them.

The Palestinian people continue to be threatened not only externally by Israel's war and political-economic violence, but also internally by ideological processes such as psychologisation, individualisation, objectification, and depoliticisation. These processes are at the heart of what Haidar Eid (2024) has described as the 'reshaping of the Palestinian mind' through 'ideological state apparatuses such as the media, education, mosques and the law' (p. 141). This includes various forms of psychology, psychiatry, and psychotherapy that have not allowed themselves to be taught and transformed by the Palestinian people. When they turn away from the people, psychologists tend to turn against the people.

REFERENCES

- Abdo, N. (2024). Racial capitalism: From British colonialism to the settler colonial apartheid state. *Journal of Holy Land and Palestine Studies*, 23(2), 187–203.
<https://doi.org/10.3366/hlps.2024.0338>
- Agbaria, N., Petzold, S., Deckert, A., Henschke, N., Veronese, G., Dambach, P., Jaenisch, T., Horstick, O., & Winkler, V. (2021). Prevalence of post-traumatic stress disorder among Palestinian children and adolescents exposed to political violence. *PLoS one*, 16(8), e0256426. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256426>
- Aitchison, R. J., Abu-Bader, S. H., Howell, M. K., Khalil, D., & Elbedour, S. (2017). Resilience in Palestinian adolescents living in Gaza. *Psychological Trauma: Theory, Research, Practice, and Policy*, 9(1), 36–43. <https://doi.org/10.1037/tra0000153>
- Aldabbour, B., Abuabada, A., Lahlouh, A., Halimy, M., Elamassie, S., Al-Karim Sammour, A., Skaik, A., & Nadarajah, S. (2024). Psychological impacts of the Gaza war on Palestinian young adults: A cross-sectional study of depression, anxiety, stress, and PTSD symptoms. *BMC Psychology*, 12(1), 696. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-024-02188-5>
- Altawil, M. (2009). El impacto psicológico del asedio en Gaza [The psychological impact of the siege on Gaza]. *Apuntes De Psicología*, 27(1), 137–148.
<https://doi.org/10.55414/ap.v27i1.1572>

- Atallah, D. G. (2022). Reflections on radical love and rebellion: Towards decolonial solidarity in community psychology praxis. In S. Kessi, S. Suffla, & M. Seedat (Eds.), *Decolonial enactments in community psychology* (pp. 75–97). Springer
- Ayer, L., Venkatesh, B., Stewart, R., Mandel, D., Stein, B., & Schoenbaum, M. (2017). Psychological aspects of the Israeli–Palestinian conflict: A systematic review. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse, 18*(3), 322–338. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1524838015613774>
- Ayyash, M. (2024). Colonial racial capitalism and violence: Theorising the relationship between empire and Israeli settler colonialism. *Journal of Holy Land and Palestine Studies, 23*(2), 205–220. <https://doi.org/10.3366/hlps.2024.0339>
- Bdier, D., & Mahamid, F. (2023). The effectiveness of a group therapeutic program based on prolonged exposure therapy in reducing posttraumatic stress disorder symptoms among a sample of Palestinian traumatized adolescents. *Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation and Mental Health, 10*(3), 277–286. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40737-022-00305-4>
- Ben-Meir, A. (2023). Psychological impediments are at the core of the Israeli–Palestinian conflict. *Politics & Policy, 51*(3), 488–503. <https://doi.org/10.1111/polp.12535>
- Chaitin, J. (2011). *Peace-building in Israel and Palestine: Social psychology and grassroots initiatives*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Costa, P. H. A., & Mendes, K. T. (2025). Lessons from psychology in Palestine: More than psychotherapy, we need a truly community psychology. *Psychotherapy & Politics International, 23*(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.24135/ppi.v23i1.08>
- Darwish, M. (2024). *Entre Rita y mis ojos, un fusil* [Between Rita and my eyes, a rifle]. Penguin.
- Dubow, E. F., Huesmann, L. R., Boxer, P., Smith, C., Landau, S., Dvir Gvirsman, S., & Shikaki, K. (2019). Serious violent behavior and antisocial outcomes as consequences of exposure to ethnic-political conflict and violence among Israeli and Palestinian youth. *Aggressive Behavior, 45*(3), 287–299. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ab.21818>
- Eid, H. (2024). *Descolonizando la mente palestina* [Decolonizing the Palestinian mind]. Verso.
- El-Astal, S. (2016). Memorias traumáticas y estrés postraumático en los niños y jóvenes palestinos de la Franja de Gaza [Traumatic memories and post-traumatic stress in Palestinian children and youth in the Gaza Strip]. *Pensando Psicología, 12*(20), 5–12. <https://doi.org/10.16925/pe.v12i20.1559>
- El-Kareh, R. (2002). Abjections. *Revue d'études palestiniennes, 2*, 95–98. <https://www.palestine-studies.org/en/node/1642793>
- Farajallah, I. (2024). Behind the Rubble: Psychological trauma of wars and human rights abuses on women and children in Gaza. *Anatolian Clinic the Journal of Medical Sciences, 29*, 119–136. <https://doi.org/10.21673/anadoluklin.1575372>
- Freud, F. (1996). Recordar, repetir y reelaborar [Remembering, repeating, and reworking]. In *Obras Completas XII* [Complete Works XII] (pp. 145–158). Amorrortu. (Original work published 1914)

- Haj-Yahia, M. M. (2007). Challenges in studying the psychological effects of Palestinian children's exposure to political violence and their coping with this traumatic experience. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 31(7), 691–697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2007.05.002>
- Hakim, N., Abi-Ghannam, G., Saab, R., Albzour, M., Zebian, Y., & Adams, G. (2023). Turning the lens in the study of precarity: On experimental social psychology's acquiescence to the settler-colonial status quo in historic Palestine. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 62(S1), 21–38. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjso.12595>
- Hammack, P. L. (2010a). The cultural psychology of Palestinian youth: A narrative approach. *Culture & Psychology*, 16(4), 507–537. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354067X10380159>
- Hammack, P. L. (2010b). *Narrative and the politics of identity: The cultural psychology of Israeli and Palestinian youth*. Oxford University Press.
- Jabr, S. (2024a). Barreiras palestinas à cura de feridas traumáticas [Palestinian barriers to healing traumatic wounds]. In R. A. Zahra (Ed.), *Sumud en tempos de genocidio* [Sumud in times of genocide] (pp. 30–34). Tabla. (Original work published 2019)
- Jabr, S. (2024b). Compreendo o trauma colonial e intergeracional [I understand colonial and intergenerational trauma]. In R. A. Zahra (Ed.), *Sumud en tempos de genocidio* [Sumud in times of genocide] (pp. 59–62). Tabla. (Original work published 2023)
- Jabr, S. (2024c). A experiência dos palestinos vai além do rótulo TEPT [The Palestinian experience goes beyond the PTSD label]. In R. A. Zahra (Ed.), *Sumud en tempos de genocidio* [Sumud in times of genocide] (pp. 55–58). Tabla. (Original work published 2019)
- Jabr, S. (2024d). A ocupação e a mente [Occupation and the mind]. In R. A. Zahra (Ed.), *Sumud en tempos de genocidio* [Sumud in times of genocide] (pp. 43–48). Tabla. (Original work published 2007)
- Jabr, S. (2024e). A ocupação no meu consultório [The occupancy in my office]. In R. A. Zahra (Ed.), *Sumud en tempos de genocidio* [Sumud in times of genocide] (pp. 27–29). Tabla. (Original work published 2019)
- Jabr, S. (2024f). A resistência à ocupação israelense é um elemento essencial na recuperação da mente ocupada [Resistance to the Israeli occupation is an essential element in the recovery of the occupied mind]. In R. A. Zahra (Ed.), *Sumud en tempos de genocidio* [Sumud in times of genocide] (pp. 116–119). Tabla. (Original work published 2021)
- Kelman, H. C. (1987). The political psychology of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. *Political Psychology*, 8(3), 347–363. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3791039>
- Losurdo, D. (2020). O sionismo e a tragédia do povo Palestino [Zionism and the tragedy of the Palestinian people]. *Crítica Marxista*, 14(24), 63–72. <https://doi.org/10.53000/cma.v14i24.19588>
- Madhoun, H. (2025). Messages from Gaza now. In M. Halasa & J. Elgrably (Eds.), *Sumud. A new Palestinian reader* (pp. 17–29). Seven Stories Press.

- Mahamid, F., Hamamra, B., & Bdier, D. (2025). Traumatic events predict sleep disturbance among Palestinians: The moderating roles of resilience and posttraumatic growth. *Traumatology*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1037/trm0000559>
- Makkawi, I. (2009). Towards an emerging paradigm of critical community psychology in Palestine. *The Journal of Critical Psychology, Counselling and Psychotherapy*, 9(2), 75–86.
- Makkawi, I. (2012). Psychology of the oppressed: Encounters with community psychology in Palestine. *Global Journal of Community Psychology Practice*, 3(4), 371–372. <https://www.gicpp.org/en/resource.php?issue=9&resource=135>
- Makkawi, I. (2017). The rise and fall of academic community psychology in Palestine and the way forward. *South African Journal of Psychology*, 47(4), 482–492. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0081246317737945>
- Marie, M., SaadAdeen, S., & Battat, M. (2020). Anxiety disorders and PTSD in Palestine: A literature review. *BMC Psychiatry*, 20, Article 509. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-020-02911-7>
- Marzouka, N., & Mazurca, R. (2005). Memoria colectiva y holocausto Palestino [Collective memory and the Palestinian Holocaust]. *Psicología para América Latina*, 4.
- Masalha, N. (2012). *The Palestine Nakba: Decolonising history, narrating the subaltern, reclaiming memory*. Zed.
- Meari, L. (2015). Reconsidering trauma: Towards a Palestinian community psychology. *Journal of Community Psychology*, 43(1), 76–86. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcop.21712>
- Mendelsohn, S. (2023). Emancipation and its discontents. *Psychotherapy & Politics International*, 21(3 & 4), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.24135/ppi.v21i3and4.13>
- Meruane, L. (2024). *Palestina en pedazos* [Palestine in pieces]. Random House.
- Palmieri, A. (2023). Palestine: A genocide: Or when psychoanalysis forgot that every symptom is political. *Psychotherapy & Politics International*, 21(3 & 4), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.24135/ppi.v21i3and4.10>
- Pappé, I. (2007). *The ethnic cleansing of Palestine*. Oneworld.
- Parker, I. (2023). Revolutionary psychoanalysts with Palestine. *Psychotherapy & Politics International*, 21(3 & 4), 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.24135/ppi.v21i3and4.12>
- Pavón-Cuellar, D. (2023). El sujeto de la psicología: reclusión, contracción, inmovilización, objetivación, inculpación, privatización y despolitización [The subject of psychology: Confinement, contraction, immobilization, objectification, incrimination, privatization and depoliticization]. *Nueva Hegemonía*, 17, 111–119. <https://nuevahegemonia.centropatria.pe/public/articulo/287>
- Punamäki, R. L., Qouta, S., & El-Sarraj, E. (2001). Resiliency factors predicting psychological adjustment after political violence among Palestinian children. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 25(3), 256–267. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01650250042000294>
- Ramdjan Azizuddin, N. S. (2024). La salud mental en tiempos de guerra: Genocidio del pueblo Palestino [Mental health in times of war: Genocide of the Palestinian people].

- Revista Psicología*, 43(1-2), 127–140.
https://saber.ucv.ve/ojs/index.php/rev_ps/article/view/29878
- Rose, J. (2005). *The question of Zion*. Princeton University Press.
- Rouhana, N. N., & Bar-Tal, D. (1998). Psychological dynamics of intractable ethnonational conflicts: The Israeli–Palestinian case. *American Psychologist*, 53(7), 761–770.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.53.7.761>
- Said, E. W. (1979). Zionism from the standpoint of its victims. *Social Text*, 1, 7–58.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/466405>
- Shalhoub-Kevorkian, N. (2020). Gun to body: Mental health against unchilding. *International Journal of Applied Psychoanalytic Studies*, 17(2), 126–145.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/aps.1652>
- Sheehi, L. & Sheehi, S. (2022). *Psychoanalysis under occupation: Practicing resistance in Palestine*. Routledge.
- Sheehi, S., & Sheehi, L. (2023). The reverie of resistance. *Psychotherapy & Politics International*, 21(3 & 4), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.24135/ppi.v21i3and4.11>
- Shejadeh, R. (2025). The road to Jerusalem: Then and now. In M. Halasa & J. Elgrably (Eds.), *Sumud. A new Palestinian Reader* (pp. 185–200). Seven Stories Press.
- Tamimi, A., & Takkuri, D. (2025). Childhood. In M. Halasa & J. Elgrably (Eds.), *Sumud. A new Palestinian reader* (pp. 153–161). Seven Stories Press.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHY

David Pavón-Cuéllar is a Mexican Marxist philosopher, Lacanian psychoanalyst, and critical psychologist. He is Professor of Psychology and Philosophy at the State University of Michoacán (Universidad Michoacana de San Nicolás de Hidalgo, Morelia, Mexico). He holds a PhD in Philosophy from the University of Rouen (France) and a PhD in Psychology from the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain). He has taught philosophy and psychoanalysis at universities in Brazil, Colombia, Mexico, Portugal, France, India, and Indonesia, among other countries. His books include *Psicoanálisis y colonialidad: hacia una inflexión anticolonial de la herencia freudiana* (Fontamara, 2024), *Then and Now: On the Crowd, the Subject, and the Collective* (with Betty Fuks, Paola Mieli, Rosalind Morris, and Alain Vanier; Agincourt, 2023), *Sobre el vacío: puentes entre marxismo y psicoanálisis* (Paradiso, 2022), *Psychoanalysis and Revolution: Critical Psychology for Liberation Movements* (with Ian Parker; 1968 Press, 2021), *Virus del Capital* (Docta Ignorancia, 2021), *Más allá de la psicología indígena: concepciones mesoamericanas de la subjetividad* (Porrúa, 2021), *Zapatismo y subjetividad: más allá de la psicología* (Cátedra Libre and UMSNH, 2020), *Psicología crítica:*

definición, antecedentes, historia y actualidad (Itaca, 2019), *Psicanálise e Marxismo: As Violências Em Tempos De Capitalismo* (with Nadir Lara; Appris, 2018), *Marxism and Psychoanalysis: In or Against Psychology?* (Routledge, 2017), and *From the Conscious Interior to an Exterior Unconscious: Lacan, Discourse Analysis and Social Psychology* (Karnac, 2010).